

Synthesis, structural and biological studies of some oxamic acids and their Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal complexes

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Manuscript received 12 March 2010, revised 21 July 2010, accepted 27 July 2010

Abstract : Six new metal complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with *N*-(4-methoxyphenyl)oxamic acid and *N*-(4-carboxyphenyl)oxamic acid have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analyses, IR, ¹H NMR and electronic spectral studies. The synthesized oxamic acids and metal complexes were screened for their biological significance against two bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* and two fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* *in vitro*. Metal complexes were found more active than their ligands. Among the complexes of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}; the Cu^{II} complexes were found most active against both the bacteria and fungi.

Keywords : Oxamic acids, metal complexes, biological studies, IR, ¹H NMR, electronic spectral studies.

Introduction

Oxamic acids, the *N*-amino derivative of aliphatic dibasic acids, exhibit extensive coordination chemistry¹ and can act as mono-, bi-, tri- and tetradentate ligands². They are also found as mono- and di-anion oxamates, forming mono-, oligo- and polymeric systems^{3,4}. Thus oxamic acids and their metal complexes have received much attention due to their diverse applications⁵⁻⁹ in analytical, industrial, biological and medicinal fields. They are also reported as antibacterial¹⁰, antifungal¹¹, anti-allergic¹², antimalarial⁵ and antihypersensitive and tumor inhibitor agents¹³. Recently, oxamic acids obtained as metabolites by the biodegradation of 4,5-dichloro-2-*n*-octyl-3(2*H*)-isothiazolin-3-one (DCOIT) have been reported as anti-fouling paints biocides¹⁴. In view of these observations, it was considered of interest to synthesize some new substituted oxamic acids and their metal complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}.

Results and discussion

The physical and analytical data of *N*-(4-methoxy-

phenyl)oxamic acid, *N*-(4-carboxyphenyl)oxamic acid and their metal complexes are given in Table 1. All the compounds were colored and non-hygroscopic in nature. The oxamic acids were soluble in methanol and ethanol whereas the metal complexes were soluble in DMSO and DMF and insoluble in common organic solvents.

In the IR spectra of oxamic acids, an absorption peak in the region of 3449–3407 cm⁻¹ was observed which may be attributed due to the OH stretching vibrations lowered from the usual range due to intramolecular H-bonding^{15,16}. In IR spectra of metal complexes, this band was absent which indicates the coordination of the ligand to the metal ion via deprotonation, which is further confirmed by the appearance of new metal M-O band¹⁷ in the region of 565–505 cm⁻¹. The IR spectra of oxamic acids exhibit a sharp intensity band in the region of 3353–3298 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed due to the presence of >NH group¹⁸. This band remains almost at same position in the metal complexes which indicates the non-participation of >NH group in the coordination. A medium intensity band in the region 1699–1680 cm⁻¹ has

Table 1. Physical properties and elemental analyses of synthesized oxamic acids and their metal complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	Molecular formula	Colour	Elemental analyses (%) :			M.p. (°C)/ Decomposition temp. (± 2 °C)
				Calcd. (Found)	Carbon	Hydrogen	
1.	NMPOA	C ₉ H ₉ O ₄ N	Light brown	55.38 (55.07)	4.65 (4.79)	7.18 (7.96)	215
2.	NCPOA	C ₉ H ₇ O ₅ N	White	51.67 (50.98)	3.38 (3.08)	6.70 (6.98)	220
3.	[Co(NMPOA) ₂]	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₈ N ₂ .Co	Dark green	48.33 (47.86)	3.61 (2.98)	6.26 (5.86)	290
4.	[Cu(NMPOA) ₂]	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₈ N ₂ .Cu	Reddish green	47.84 (47.20)	3.57 (4.06)	6.20 (6.86)	280
5.	[Ni(NMPOA) ₂]	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₈ N ₂ .Ni	Brownish green	48.35 (49.26)	3.61 (2.80)	6.27 (5.98)	300
6.	[Co(NCPOA) ₂]	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₁₀ N ₂ .Co	Dark pink	45.48 (44.28)	2.55 (2.20)	5.89 (6.28)	285
7.	[Cu(NCPOA) ₂]	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₁₀ N ₂ .Cu	Dark brown	45.04 (46.30)	2.52 (2.12)	5.84 (5.92)	280
8.	[Ni(NCPOA) ₂]	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₁₀ N ₂ .Ni	Green	45.50 (44.84)	2.55 (2.10)	5.89 (6.50)	290

been appeared in the IR spectra of oxamic acids which may be attributed due to $>CO$ stretching vibrations. The position of this band has shifted towards lower side in the case of metal complexes which clearly indicates the coordination of ligands with the metal ion through carbonyl oxygen. The bands in the region of $1385\text{--}1333\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1295\text{--}1292\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to the presence of $-C-N$ and $>CO$ moiety respectively. A medium sharp intensity band in the region of $1250\text{--}1240\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the IR spectra of the oxamic acids and their metal complexes indicate an interaction between $N-H$ bending and $C-N$ stretching vibrations.

1H NMR spectra of the synthesized oxamic acids were recorded in DMSO solvent. Both the ligands show a multiplet in the range of δ 6.5–8.0 ppm due to aromatic protons¹⁹, a singlet in the region δ 3.0–5.5 ppm due to the protons of $-NH_2$ group and a singlet in the range of δ 10.5–12.0 ppm due to the proton of $-COOH$ group. An unsymmetrical pattern of proton of benzene ring appeared in the region of δ 6.9–7.6 ppm²⁰.

In the electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes, a weak band in the region $18331\text{--}18044\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to transition $^2E_g \rightarrow ^2T_{2g}$ and one intense band at 16318 cm^{-1}

(CT band), suggest the square planar²¹ geometry of the complexes.

The electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes exhibit a broad band in the region $19888\text{--}19230\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may correspond to the transitions $^2E_g \rightarrow ^2T_{2g}$ indicating square planar geometry²² for these complexes.

In the electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes, a broad band around $19504\text{--}19135\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and an intense band has been noted around $28571\text{--}28392\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (CT band). The appearance of these bands suggests the square planar geometry²³ for these complexes.

Based on elemental analyses, IR, 1H NMR and electronic spectral studies, square planar structures have been suggested for all the complexes (Fig. 1).

Experimental

The purity of all the synthesized compounds was checked by running their TLC for single spot on silica gel-G plates and by repeated melting point determination of the recrystallized samples in open capillaries (Table 1). Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were carried out on Thomas CH-analyser 35 Carlo Erba-1106 and Coleman-N-analyser. IR spectra were recorded on

Fig. 1. Probable structure of metal complexes.

Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer model Rx 1 using KBr pellets. 1H NMR spectra were recorded on NMR spectrometer model Bruker DRX-300. Electronic spectra were recorded on model ultrascan UV 2600 double beam spectrometer in DMSO solution at room temperature.

Synthesis of *N*-(4-methoxyphenyl)oxamic acid (NMPOA) : A mixture of *p*-anisidine (0.02 mol, 2.46 g) and diethyl oxalate (0.02 mol, 2.7 ml) was refluxed for 2 h using air condenser. After cooling the contents, 20 ml absolute alcohol was added. The insoluble oxamide, formed during this reaction, was filtered out and an aqueous solution of sodium carbonate was added to the filtrate. The mixture was steam distilled and then concentrated HCl was added to obtain precipitate. The obtained light brown crystalline product was filtered, washed with distilled water and recrystallized from ethanol. It was dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ in a vacuum desiccator under reduced pressure. Similarly, *N*-(4-carboxyphenyl)oxamic acid (NCPOA) was synthesized by the reaction of *p*-amino benzoic acid and diethyl oxalate.

Synthesis of metal complexes : Metal complexes were synthesized by the reaction of 10–15 ml methanolic solution of NMPOA/NCPOA (0.002 mol) with aqueous solutions (0.001 mol) of metal acetates (0.249 g, $(CH_3COO)_2Co \cdot 4H_2O$ /0.199 g, $(CH_3COO)_2Cu \cdot H_2O$ /0.248 g, $(CH_3COO)_2Ni \cdot 4H_2O$). The mixtures were stirred over a magnetic stirrer and then refluxed for 3–4 h. On cooling, colored precipitates were obtained. Products were filtered and washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ in a desiccator.

Biological studies :

All the synthesized compounds, oxamic acids as well as their metal complexes, were screened for their antimicrobial activity against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram positive) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram negative) at 37 °C for 24 h and fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* in suitable nutrient medium at 28 °C for 96 h by adopting Serial Dilution Method²⁴. A comparative study of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) values in general, infer that biological activity of oxamic acids has increased in the form of their metal complexes. Among the metal complexes of Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} , the Cu^{II} complexes were found most active against both the bacteria and fungi.

Table 2. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) values in molar concentration ($\times 10^{-3}$) of oxamic acids and their metal complexes

Sl. no.	Comps.	Bacteria		Fungi	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>
1.	Ligands				
a.	<i>N</i> -(4-Carboxyphenyl)oxamic acid (NCPOA)	59.8	59.8	29.9	29.9
b.	<i>N</i> -(4-Methoxyphenyl)oxamic acid (NMPOA)	58.1	58.1	29.0	29.0
2.	Metal complexes				
a.	I. $Co(NCPOA)_2$	52.6	52.6	26.3	26.3
	II. $Cu(NCPOA)_2$	26.0	26.0	13.0	13.0
	III. $Ni(NCPOA)_2$	52.6	26.3	26.3	26.3
b.	I. $Co(NMPOA)_2$	43.1	43.1	21.5	21.5
	II. $Cu(NMPOA)_2$	22.3	22.3	11.1	11.1
	III. $Ni(NMPOA)_2$	41.6	41.6	20.8	20.8

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